

RNA Extraction and Measurement - COSMOS

Forked from [RNA Extraction and Measurement](#)

ABSTRACT

This beginner-friendly protocol extracts RNA using Qiagen's RNeasy Plus Mini Kit and measures RNA concentration using invitrogen's Qubit RNA HS Assay Kit.

Protocol Info: Jasmine Sakr: RNA Extraction and Measurement - COSMOS. [protocols.io](https://protocols.io/view/rna-extraction-and-measurement-cosmos-cw24xggw) <https://protocols.io/view/rna-extraction-and-measurement-cosmos-cw24xggw>

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GUIDELINES

Make sure all tubes are labeled properly, including group name or number and what is in the tube.

MATERIALS

EQUIPMENT/ SUPPLIES

- Qubit Fluorometer
- Qubit Assay Tubes
- 1.5 mL Tubes
- RNeasy Plus Mini Kit

REAGENTS

Light sensitive dyes (keep in dark):

- Qubit RNA HS Assay Kit

Keep at room temp:

- Nuclease-free H₂O

BEFORE START INSTRUCTIONS

Make sure to do all the calculations and make fresh ethanol.

The Tubes

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Make sure to label all tubes!

Safety information

The blue color solution used in the following images is just for illustration; none of the Qiagen buffers are blue in color. Also, volumes used are not to scale.

Preparation

2 Make 70% Ethanol

One of the wash steps will use 70% ethanol.

Note

70% Ethanol Calculation

1. First calculate how much ethanol you need
2. Then calculation how to make ethanol concentration 70%

EXAMPLE:

Total volume of ethanol

$$\text{ethanol } \boxed{300 \mu\text{L}} \times (4 \text{ samples} + 0.5) = \boxed{1350 \mu\text{L}}$$

Ethanol concentration

$$\{1350 \mu\text{L}\} \times \{0.7\} = \{945 \mu\text{L}\} \text{ of 100\% ethanol}$$

$$\{1350 \mu\text{L}\} - \{945 \mu\text{L}\} = \{405 \mu\text{L}\} \text{ of Nuclease-free H}_2\text{O}$$

Making 70% ethanol

$$\boxed{945 \mu\text{L}} \text{ 100\% ethanol} + \boxed{405 \mu\text{L}} \text{ Nuclease-free H}_2\text{O} = \boxed{1350 \mu\text{L}} \text{ of 70\% ethanol}$$

Extraction Overview

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RNeasy Plus Procedure

Total time: <25 minutes

Image provided by Qiagen handbook

Lyse Cells

4 Lysis buffer was previously added to the cells in the tissue culture plates

30s

1. Thaw the plate with cells + lysis buffer (called a lysate)
2. Pipet the lysate up and down then transfer to a new labeled 1.5 mL tube
3. Vortex for 00:00:30

Remove gDNA

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1. Transfer the homogenized lysate to the gDNA Eliminator spin column (in a collection tube) with a pipet
2. Centrifuge for 15000 rpm
3. Discard the column, and **SAVE** the flow-through.

Safety information

Make sure the tubes are arranged symmetrically in the centrifuge! **Running a centrifuge unbalanced can damage it.**

Examples of symmetrical arrangements in a microcentrifuge. [\[Image Credit\]](#)

Safety information

DO NOT discard the flow-through! The gDNA Eliminator spin column captures the gDNA in the filter and the RNA is passed through with the solution.

Ethanol Wash

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1m

1. Add **600 μ L** of **70% ethanol** to the flow-through in the collection tube
2. Mix well by pipetting
3. Transfer half (about **600 μ L**) to an RNeasy spin column (in a collection tube) with a pipet
4. Centrifuge for **00:00:30** at **15000 rpm**
5. Discard flow-through
6. Transfer the rest into the **SAME** RNeasy spin column (in a collection tube) with a pipet
7. Centrifuge for **00:00:30** at **15000 rpm**
8. Discard flow-through

Buffer Washes

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1. Add **700 μ L** **Buffer RW1** to the RNeasy Mini spin column (in a collection tube)
2. Centrifuge for **00:00:30** at **15000 rpm**
3. Discard flow-through
4. Add **500 μ L** **Buffer RPE** to the RNeasy Mini spin column (in a collection tube)
5. Centrifuge for **00:00:30** at **15000 rpm**
6. Discard flow-through
7. *Repeat.* Add **500 μ L** **Buffer RPE** to the RNeasy Mini spin column (in a collection tube)
8. *Repeat.* Centrifuge for **00:01:00** at **15000 rpm**
9. *Repeat.* Discard flow-through

10. **WITHOUT** adding any buffers, centrifuge for 15000 rpm (this is called a "dry" spin)

Elute RNA

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1. Take the RNeasy spin column **OUT** of the collection tube and into a new labeled 1.5 mL tube.
2. Add 40 μL Nuclease-free H_2O directly **OVER** the spin column membrane at the bottom of the column
3. Incubate for 00:05:00
4. Centrifuge for 15000 rpm

Measure RNA Concentration

2m 3s

- 9 Measure RNA concentration with the Qubit Fluorometer.

9.1 Dilute Sample

The kit we use is very sensitive and detects a low range of RNA concentration, so we have to make a **separate** sample dilution to use when we measure concentration.

Note

Dilutions EXAMPLE:

We are going to make a 1:10 dilution (1 to 10 dilution), which means our dilute sample will be 10 times more dilute than the original sample.

Making 1:10 Dilution

- $1\ \mu\text{L}$ sample + $9\ \mu\text{L}$ Nuclease-free H_2O = $10\ \mu\text{L}$ diluted sample

9.2 Make the following Qubit master mix at Room temperature

Safety information

Keep the *Qubit RNA HS Reagent* (dye) closed and in the dark when not in use!

Note

Master Mix Calculation

Each sample requires $199\ \mu\text{L}$ buffer + $1\ \mu\text{L}$ dye. To make enough for all of your samples, calculate the following:

buffer $199\ \mu\text{L}$ x (# samples + 0.5)

dye $1\ \mu\text{L}$ x (# samples + 0.5)

Total master mix volume = buffer + dye

- 9.3
1. Label a new Qubit Assay tube for each sample
 2. Add $199\ \mu\text{L}$ of Qubit Master Mix
 3. Add $1\ \mu\text{L}$ RNA of *diluted* sample (for information)
 4. Incubate Room temperature for $00:02:00$
 5. Insert each tube into the Qubit Fluorometer
 6. Click "RNA HS" and follow the on screen instructions

2m 3s

9.4 Determining original RNA stock concentration

Since we used a dilution to find concentration, we need to multiply the concentration we get from the Qubit by the dilution factor.

Note

For a 1:10 dilution, the dilution factor is 10 because our original sample is 10 times more concentrated.

EXAMPLE:

$$[M] 53 \text{ ng}/\mu\text{L} \times 10 = [M] 530 \text{ ng}/\mu\text{L} \text{ original sample concentration}$$

NOTES

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